

TENDENCIES TO REDUCE THE LEVEL OF POVERTY AND INCREASE THE STANDARD OF LIVING OF THE POPULATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article analyzes the level of poverty existing in the country today, the problems related to it, and targeted, practical measures to solve them. Also, the authors made suggestions and recommendations for improving the well-being and quality of life of the population.

Key words. Poverty, level of poverty, quality of life, standard of living, population income, labor market, unemployment, economic growth, human capital, social protection, living wage, inclusive business.

Introduction

Rapid development of digital techniques and technologies has different effects on the economy of countries. In particular, modern digital professions are emerging instead of many professions in the labor market, the reduction of jobs due to the digitization of industries and networks is causing problems related to unemployment. And this, in turn, leads to a decrease in the standard of living of the population in countries where a large part of the population's income is made up of wages. Therefore, one of the urgent problems facing countries in the digital economy is to ensure a comfortable life by increasing the standard of living and quality of life of the population.

In our country, many measures are being implemented in order to increase the standard of living of the population, the level of employment and the mobility of modern jobs and labor resources. In particular, by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, in the concept of socio-economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, in order to ensure macroeconomic stability and stability of economic growth, the competitiveness of economic sectors, and increase the income of the population between different layers of the population. In order to create favorable conditions for the development and protection of entrepreneurship, reduce the level of tension in the labor market, and reduce poverty, on December 3, 2021, the "Concept of the socio-economic complex development of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" was adopted. In the concept, improving the standard of living of the population and reducing poverty, improving the regulatory framework for poverty assessment and reduction, creating labor-intensive jobs, supporting the poor and vulnerable people and their capital special attention is paid to increasing, strengthening the addressability and effectiveness of the social protection system, and improving the quality of social protection services.[1]

Despite the fact that scientists have given different definitions to the concept of poverty, its meaning has not yet been fully revealed. Some economists consider poverty to be the inability to meet basic human needs, while others consider it to be insufficient freedom of

choice or the constant presence of social, educational, and health barriers that undermine a person's participation in the socio-economic life of society. refers to the scope.[2]

In general, in the world experience, poverty is a concept that describes economic conditions such as insufficient minimum needs for a person or social group to live, ability to work, and the ability to continue their generation.[3]

In our country, many scientists are conducting a number of researches in this regard. For example, Qalandar Abdurahmanov in his textbook "Economics of Labor" defined poverty as the consumption of benefits at the level of maintaining working capacity as the lower limit of re-creating resources for labor.[4]

In our opinion, poverty is an indicator that expresses the quality of life and standard of living of members of the society and is characterized by the minimal level of satisfaction of the needs necessary for living.

Analysis and results. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his address to the parliament on January 24, 2020, spoke for the first time about the poor segment of the population of Uzbekistan, saying that 12-15 percent of the population of the republic are poor, their total number is 4.5-5 million. emphasized. And it was determined as one of the main tasks to carry out practical work on the elimination of this problem, the development of targeted measures to increase the population's income and thereby improve the standard and quality of life, and the formation of a system of indicators that accurately describe the level of poverty.[5]

Also, the following indirect and direct factors influencing the impoverishment of the population can be listed:

1. Mainly in rural areas, the population does not have enough knowledge and skills, and as a result, they cannot withstand competition in the labor market;
2. Negative results in the educational system and low quality of medicine in the regions;
3. The high level of patronizing sentiment in some strata of the population, the presence of excessive spending in national traditions;
4. High level of unemployment in some regions, lack of creation of new jobs, low income and low standard of living, etc.

If the opposite of these indicators happens, i.e., production develops, knowledge and skills, employment, competitiveness indicators increase in the labor market, material growth will increase by itself.

According to the World Bank, a high level of poverty in Uzbekistan is observed in Samarkand, Surkhandarya, Syrdarya, Andijan regions and the Republic of Karakalpakstan.[6]

There are several limits in determining this, and a certain standard is set for a decent living of the population. If a person's income (or expenses) is below the specified standard, he is considered poor.

1. The poverty line is determined by assessing the expenses or income received for the purchase of the minimum daily amount of food and necessary products, as well as the family's ability to use a certain group of goods and services. For example, according to the methodology of measuring poverty of the State Statistics Committee, people who consume (spend) less than 2100 kcal per day in Uzbekistan are called poor.[7]

2. At the end of 2019, the gross domestic product per capita in Uzbekistan was 1,723 US dollars, which was the basis for entering the republic into the group of low-middle income countries according to the World Bank classification.[8]

3. In the report published by the Ministry of Finance for April-May 2020, about 1 million 772 thousand citizens (42.6 percent) of citizens who earn wages and pay personal income tax up to 100 dollars, 1 million 66,000 people receive between \$100 and \$200 a month.[9]

In recent years, significant progress has been made in creating a publicly available database that can be used to study poverty. They allow us to test many hypotheses about the description of poverty, its causes, and the impact of specific programs and policy reforms on poverty.

Based on the factors affecting poverty, its distribution can be divided into the following types:

Rural families whose welfare depends mainly on agricultural activities. The following are typical for these families[15]:

- a relatively high level of employment by hiring and a stable ratio of the number of employed and unemployed members of the family (the ratio is 1:1.5);
- low level of professional education of older members of the family;
- low productivity of existing land areas due to lack of water and low quality of land;
- the size of the family and the excess of the economic burden on the employed members of the family. A threat factor for these families is the low and unstable incomes that depend on the market conditions of agricultural products and external factors of agricultural activities. More families living in small towns, urban-type settlements, and county centers. This category consists of hired employees of non-agricultural enterprises. The following characteristics are characteristic of these families:

- the family does not eat very much (close to the average);
- the relative size of the economic burden falling on employed members of the family;
- a much higher level of education of the household head;
- low level of employment of able-bodied members of the family;
- lack of land area and small size.

The risk factors for these families are the increase in prices for consumer goods and services, the delay in wages, and the deterioration of the economic situation of non-agricultural enterprises that make up the structure.

Urban families fall into this type and are distinguished by the following features:

- that the family is not very big;
- the size of the economic burden that falls on employed people at the expense of both schoolchildren and older unemployed members of the family;
- the incompleteness of the family, that is, the absence of one of the breadwinners;
- employment of able-bodied members of the family in budget areas;
- lack of land area.

Conclusions and recommendations. Anti-poverty recommendations are based on the characteristics of low-income households, socio-economic barriers to participation in community life, and promising directions for development, as well as policies at the macroeconomic and micro levels, which determine their success. .

It is desirable to fight poverty and prevent it in several directions:

- economic measures aimed at increasing the standard of living of an individual employee and the general population (these are incomes, employment policy, investment, tax, targeted social assistance);

- to increase the efficiency of the system of objectively protecting the population from various risks (loss of working capacity, illness, disability, unemployment, old age, death, loss of a breadwinner) and the system of granting allowances to children and special groups of the population;

- improvement of the system of social assistance (material or non-material assistance, free meals, assistance in restoring the rights of disabled people, providing social services at home, in day care institutions, providing social housing).

The redistribution of income in favor of the poor through different types of assistance as a result of changes in taxation is not effective in poverty alleviation. Most developed countries have already abandoned such a path. Providing assistance to the poor in the form of payment leads to a decrease in the incentive function of wages, the development of a sentiment of poverty, the deterioration of the composition of employment, the appearance of people who are completely deprived of the desire to improve their situation. will help.

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